

Appearance Meets Geometry: Deep Learning for Semantic Segmentation in Archaeological Fortification Studies

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ABSTRACT

Modern archaeological practice faces a critical bottleneck: while photogrammetric surveys routinely generate terabytes of high-resolution 3D data from ancient fortifications, manual interpretation methods remain time-consuming and subjective, leaving much documentation underexploited. This paper presents a novel machine-learning workflow that bridges the gap between high-throughput data acquisition and efficient analysis by leveraging both appearance and geometric information from 3D photogrammetric models for automated masonry semantic segmentation.

Our approach transforms 3D documentation into a dual-layer format combining high-resolution orthomosaics with geometry-based normal maps derived from heightmap data. We trained convolutional neural networks on annotated datasets from Carian fortification walls currently spanning approximately 700 m across the ancient sites of Halicarnassus and Cedreae. The training dataset comprises 1,876 m² of wall facade with 5,560 individually annotated stones across several masonry classes.

Comparative evaluation of appearance-only, geometry-only, and combined models demonstrates clear performance advantages for the integrated approach. The combined model achieved a 17% improvement over appearance-only models and 12% over geometry-only approaches.

These results confirm that visual and geometric features provide complementary information essential for robust archaeological analysis. The automated pipeline enables processing of kilometer-long fortifications in minutes rather than weeks, transforming archaeological documentation from selective sampling to comprehensive analysis of entire defensive systems. This work represents a concrete step toward realizing photogrammetry's analytical potential, enabling systematic comparative studies across sites and periods at unprecedented scales.

Keywords: semantic segmentation, photogrammetry, normal maps, fortification architecture, deep learning, machine learning, masonry classification, 3D documentation, Carian fortifications

Introduction

Over the past few decades, archaeological practice has undergone a major shift due to the rapid development of digital documentation technologies (Moullou et al. 2023: 107–109). Total stations and GPS systems have become standard tools in the field (Sylaiou et al. 2025: 4–5), while high-resolution digital photography, (drone-based) photogrammetry and sometimes even laser scanning now enable us to capture large amounts of ancient remains in great detail (Müth et al. 2016: ix; Sylaiou et al. 2025: 2–17). Especially working with monumental buildings, such as ancient fortifications, has benefited enormously from new technologies: even poorly preserved walls can easily extend to several kilometers and, thanks to modern documentation methods, can still be documented digitally in a comparatively time-efficient manner.

These gains in documentational speed and quality lead to a need for new methods for interpretational work: the sheer volume of 3D and image-based data far outpaces our capacity for manual analysis. Photogrammetric surveys routinely generate terabytes of mesh and texture data, yet conventional approaches to wall-surface interpretation, such as drawing plans by hand, manual segmentation of masonry types, or textual description and comparison remain time consuming and to a certain extent subjective. As a result, many excavated or surveyed fortification segments might already be digitally documented but lie underexploited, making comparative studies across sites inconsistent and difficult to achieve.

To bridge this gap between high-throughput data acquisition and efficient, reproducible analysis, this paper presents a novel machine-learning workflow to segment ancient fortification masonry from 3D documentation.¹

Our core observation is that 3D documentation provides a scalable and convenient way to include both appearance and geometric information into the process (Couprie et al. 2013; Gupta et al. 2014). Specifically, we feed both RGB observations and normal maps into a convolutional neural network (CNN) (Lecun et al. 1998) to perform semantic segmentation.

Our approach transforms 3D data by using a combination of high-resolution orthomosaics and geometry-based normal maps, which together provide both visual and geometric information in a suitable format, to train a CNN. This allows the model to recognize not only individual stones but also classify different block types and to work reliably even under diverse lighting conditions and levels of preservation.

The following sections describe the archaeological context of this work, data acquisition, preparation, and augmentation, training the neural network and evaluation results demonstrating improved classification accuracy compared to conventional 2D approaches.

Archaeological Context & Research Problem

Classical fortification studies evolved significantly through foundational work by Bean and Cook in the 1950s, who documented Carian fortifications and established their association with Maussollos and the Hellenistic tradition (Bean and Cook 1957: 140; Bean, Cook and Pease 1955: 169). This early scholarship focused primarily on architectural descriptions, chronological sequences, and historical contextualization within broader political and military frameworks (Karlsson 1994: 142–143).

¹ The method described here constitutes the first part of Nils Schnorr's ongoing PhD thesis, supervised by Prof. Dr. Katharina Meinecke (Saarland University) and Dr. Thomas Leimkühler (Max Planck Institute for Informatics). The complete methodological framework, along with extended case studies and statistical-analysis modules, will be presented at a later time during this doctoral project.

89 The field advanced substantially with the Focus on Fortifications Project (2008–2011),
90 producing comprehensive publications covering regions from Spain to Central Asia and periods
91 from 3rd millennium BC to 6th century AD, moving beyond descriptive approaches toward
92 analytical methodologies examining defensive architecture's social, political, and economic
93 functions (Frederiksen et al. 2016; Muth et al. 2016).

94
95 Roughly from that time on, rapid advances in digital documentation technologies have
96 fundamentally altered archaeological practice. Methods like photogrammetry have evolved from
97 being a specialized tool into becoming part of every field-archaeologist's toolkit (Marín-Buzón et
98 al. 2021: 22) and indispensable in documenting, especially when it comes to large scale objects.

99 Often described as revolutionary, these new methods of documentation have massively
100 impacted the way modern archaeologists work and exponentially increased the digital information
101 available (Hostettler et al. 2024; Pendić and Molly 2024: 9–10; Wyatt-Spratt 2022).

102 However, these technological advances have created significant challenges. Current digital
103 documentation approaches face substantial limitations in standardization, data management, and
104 long-term preservation, although consistent data protocols are gradually becoming increasingly
105 common in archaeology (Sylaiou et al. 2025: 19–20). The lack of unified standards for
106 photogrammetric surveys creates difficulties in inter-project comparison, while the massive
107 datasets require substantial computational resources for processing and storage. These limitations
108 have created what Magnani et al. identified as a critical gap: while photogrammetry is "widely used
109 as a visual aid, its analytical potential remains underdeveloped." (Magnani et al. 2020: 737).

110
111 At this discrepancy between data documentation and analytical potential, this paper proposes
112 a novel two-layer pipeline that transforms photogrammetric documentation from passive visual
113 records into active analytical tools. This approach leverages the full 3D nature of modern
114 archaeological documentation by combining visual and geometric information for machine
115 learning-based analysis. Enabling archaeologists to automatically segment fortification walls on a
116 large scale will allow for new approaches in understanding and comparing building characteristics
117 across walls of different sites and regions.

118
119 To segment the fortification walls for further analysis, a pipeline had to be developed, in which
120 the 3D photogrammetric documentation is transformed into a 2D format without sacrificing
121 geometric facade information. Traditional archaeological image segmentation relies mostly on 2D
122 RGB data, processing only visual texture without incorporating the geometric details captured
123 during 3D documentation (Bellat et al. 2025: 18 for an overview on recent segmentation
124 development). Workflows that approach surface-classification of 3D objects rely on 2D texture
125 maps and therefore also neglect the geometric properties of the objects (Grilli and Remondino
126 2019: 14). Existing approaches for converting 3D data into 2D representations can be found in
127 LiDAR-based methods, converting terrain data into slope visualizations to segment broad
128 topographic features (Landauer et al. 2025: 53; Verschoof-van Der Vaart and Lambers 2019: 37).
129 Due to the inherent limitations of this acquisition technique, such methods can not include any
130 visual appearances of the terrain and do not detect the fine-scale geometry essential for masonry
131 analysis. Our approach addresses this limitation through a novel dual-layer methodology that
132 combines high-resolution orthomosaics with geometry-based normal maps derived from close-
133 range photogrammetric models. This transformation preserves both visual texture and critical
134 surface orientation information in a format suitable for standard CNN architectures. Unlike previous
135 3D-to-2D approaches that encode broad topographic features, our normal maps capture fine-scale
136 surface geometry essential for masonry analysis – enabling the network to distinguish between
137 masonry types based on both visual characteristics and surface topography. This approach proves
138 particularly robust for analyzing weathered ancient fortifications under different lighting conditions,
139 where traditional segmentation based on mere appearance have yielded mixed results (Bellat et
140 al. 2025: 24–25).

Materials and Methods

142 Our approach transforms high-resolution 3D photogrammetric models of fortification walls into
 143 automatically segmented facades with each stone classified by masonry type. The dry-stone
 144 fortification walls of classical antiquity typically comprise four categories: ashlar blocks, polygonal
 145 blocks, trapezoid blocks, and quarry stones (McNicoll and Milner 1997: 18; Nöth 2023: 4; Winter
 146 1971: 80), all illustrated in Fig. 1. To achieve multi-class segmentation of these types, we
 147 implement a 2D processing pipeline that operates on orthographic projections of the facades,
 148 encoding both visual appearance (RGB) and surface geometry as pixel-based data layers. This
 149 dual-layer approach feeds a convolutional neural network, enabling us to leverage the full
 150 informational richness of modern archaeological documentation. An overview of this pipeline is
 151 shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 1: Categories of dry-stone fortification walls considered in this work. Color patches indicate the scheme used to visualize the categories in segmentation maps.

Figure 2: Overview of the proposed pipeline. From a photogrammetric 3D reconstruction of the wall, 2D appearance and geometry layers are extracted and fed into a machine-learning model that predicts a multi-class semantic segmentation (colors denote individual classes, see Fig. 1). The greyed-out elements represent manual annotations used during training, while the non-greyed components form the inference pipeline.

152 Study Sites and Data Acquisition

153 For this approach, the Carian (Fig. 3) “Geländemauern” (also referred to as “great circuit”)
 154 (Bessac and Müth 2020: 23; Paksoy and Baran 2023: 40; Pimouguet-Pédarros 2000: 106)
 155 represent a good dataset for training machine learning models designed to detect and classify dry-
 156 stone fortification walls across diverse geographical contexts throughout classical antiquity. Easily
 157 spanning over several kilometers, these walls usually demonstrate multiple construction and repair
 158 phases spanning several centuries, resulting in exceptional architectural diversity. Prominent
 159 examples for these diverse “Geländemauern” can be found in Kaunos (Özen 2023; Schmalz
 160 2010) and Halicarnassus (Pedersen 2010, 2023). During the collaborative campaigns between
 161 Saarland University, Germany, and the Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University, Turkey, in the years 2022–
 162 2024, approximately 2 km of fortification walls from the ancient cities of Halicarnassus and Cedrae
 163 (Diler et al. 2024) could be documented for this methodological approach. These walls were
 164 documented through drone-based photogrammetry and RTK-GPS systems, generating highly

165 accurate 3D models. From the comprehensive photogrammetric documentation, the orthomosaics
166 (Mavromati, Petsa and Karras 2002), consisting of RGB- and Alpha-channels, were produced for
167 each wall facade. The alpha-channel inherently separates the potential wall from the background.
168 Furthermore, to acquire depth-information, corresponding heightmaps were produced to match
169 each orthomosaic.

Figure 3: Study area with geographical context and ancient sites of the region.

170 From Depth to Surface Orientation: Normal Map Generation

171 While heightmaps provide valuable depth information, their raw values are scale-dependent
172 and can vary dramatically between different photogrammetric captures, making them unsuitable
173 for direct use in machine-learning models. Therefore, the heightmaps were transformed into
174 normal maps for the machine-learning workflow (Fig. 4). Normal maps are computed from the
175 depth data using finite differencing to estimate surface gradients. For each pixel in the heightmap,
176 we calculate the partial derivatives in both horizontal and vertical directions by examining the depth
177 differences between neighboring pixels. These derivatives, representing the rate of change of the
178 surface height in each direction, are used to construct 3D surface normal vectors per pixel that
179 encode surface orientation through RGB color channels (Cohen, Olano and Manocha 1998;
180 Mikkelsen 2008). This representation of surface orientation is inherently normalized, ensuring our
181 method remains robust when applied to walls of varying depths or from different photogrammetric
182 datasets. This approach allows the CNN to process both visual features from orthomosaics and
183 geometric relationships encoded in the normal maps.

Figure 4: Depth maps (left) provide absolute distance information, which complicates standardization. Our pipeline instead uses normal maps (right), which encode local surface orientation. For reference, the color coding of surface normals is illustrated using a sphere in the top right.

184

185 Training Data Preparation

186 For training data preparation, the orthomosaics of the facades were systematically annotated
 187 using a refined three-class masonry typology: ashlar blocks, polygonal blocks, and quarry stones.
 188 While ultimately interested in distinguishing four masonry types found in ancient Greek and Carian
 189 fortification traditions, trapezoid blocks were strategically included within the ashlar training class
 190 due to their sparse occurrence in the archaeological record, which would otherwise result in
 191 insufficient training data. The two classes can then be separated in post-processing based on the
 192 trapezoid block's characteristic non-orthogonal corners. This geometric-based separation,
 193 however, is generally not feasible for the other masonry types – weathered ashlar and polygonal
 194 blocks, for instance, may share similar geometries but differ in spatial context and textural patterns
 195 that ML-based classification can reliably distinguish. Manual segmentation masks have been
 196 created so far for approximately 700 meters of documented walls, covering 1,876 m² of wall facade
 197 and resulting in 5,560 individually annotated stones. Each masonry type was assigned specific
 198 discrete labels to ensure consistent classification throughout the training dataset. The annotated
 199 dataset comprised 1,704 ashlar blocks, 1,875 polygonal stones and 1,981 quarry stones.
 200 (Bhattiprolu 2024 was used for annotation).

201 To prepare the orthomosaics, normal maps and annotations for training, the large images were
 202 cut into tiles, each covering on average 5 m² of wall facade. This area was chosen to maintain
 203 visual clarity of individual stone features while simultaneously ensuring sufficient surrounding
 204 context for each stone's position within the facade. These patches were subsequently
 205 downsampled to 512 × 512 pixels, resulting in resolutions ranging from 1.75 to 6.25 mm/px for the
 206 training. To avoid systematic biases, we employed a Sobol sequence (Sobol 1967) for pseudo-
 207 random patch positions, targeting 160% area coverage to ensure sufficient overlap and provide
 208 multiple contextual views during training (Fig. 5). Tiles containing only background pixels were
 209 excluded, ensuring that each training sample included at least partial wall surface data. This
 210 preprocessing pipeline resulted in a diverse yet representative dataset that captured both fine
 211 grained stone textures and their broader architectural context.

212

213 Archaeological 3D documentation often produces limited datasets, which can lead to overfitting
 214 when training neural networks. Data augmentation addresses this by creating synthetic variations
 215 of existing data (Alomar, Aysel and Cai 2023: 5; Banasiak et al. 2022: 9; Shorten and Khoshgoftaar
 216 2019: 7). However, our normal maps, which encode 3D surface information as directional RGB
 217 values, constrained our augmentation options. We applied horizontal flipping, implementing it after
 218 exporting orthomosaics and heightmaps but before normal map generation. This preserves both

219 the geometric integrity of surface normals and archaeological plausibility, while effectively doubling
 220 our training dataset.

Figure 5: Illustration of training data generation: image patches are cropped at quasi-random positions across the wall, shown as red boxes.

221 The resulting tiles combine orthomosaics and normal maps into seven-channel images (three
 222 RGB channels, one alpha channel, and three normal map channels), paired with corresponding
 223 masks containing four classes (one background and three block type classes).

224 Training the Model

225 The patched images are used as input for a standard U-Net (Ronneberger, Fischer and Brox
 226 2015) with the following architecture:

$$(16)_2^3 \blacktriangleright (32)_2^3 \blacktriangleright (64)_2^3 \blacktriangleright (128)_2^3 \blacktriangleright (256)_2^3 \blacktriangleleft (128)_2^3 \blacktriangleleft (64)_2^3 \blacktriangleleft (32)_2^3 \blacktriangleleft (16)_2^3 (4)_1^1$$

227 where $(\ell)_r^k$ denotes r blocks of $k \times k$ convolution with ℓ channels with ReLU activations and
 228 dropout regularization, \blacktriangleright denotes 2×2 max-pooling, \blacktriangleleft is 2×2 bilinear upsampling, and
 229 concatenation is used for skip-connections. The network processes a 7-channel input (combining
 230 RGB, Alpha and geometry) and produces 4-class segmentations. Training employed the Adam
 231 optimizer (Kingma and Ba 2015) with a hybrid loss ($0.5 \times \text{cross-entropy} + 0.5 \times \text{Dice}$) (Milletari,
 232 Navab and Ahmadi 2016) to address class imbalance in the archaeological masonry dataset.
 233

234 Evaluation

235 Protocol

236 To assess the generalization capability of our approach, we implemented a deliberate data
 237 partitioning strategy that tests both intra-site and inter-site performance. From the comprehensive
 238 annotation dataset comprising 1,876 m² of wall facade containing 5,560 individually segmented
 239 stones, we reserved approximately 16% (310 m²) distributed across four wall facades as an
 240 independent test set, completely withheld from the training process (Table 1). While three of these
 241 test walls originate from the primary documentation sites of Cedrae and Halicarnassus, one wall
 242 was selected from Kaunos – a geographically distinct Carian site – to evaluate the model's ability
 243 to generalize across regional architectural variations within a broader fortification tradition.
 244

245 The remaining 84% of the data (1,566 m²) formed the basis for model development, with a
 246 standard 90/10 split automatically applied for training and validation during the optimization
 247 process.

Name	Site	Classes	Surface Area	Purpose
Wall 1	Halicarnassus	All classes	121 m ²	Balanced evaluation
Wall 2	Cedraee	Ashlar (dominant) & Quarry	53 m ²	Class imbalance test
Wall 3	Cedraee	Polygonal (dominant) & Quarry	66 m ²	Class imbalance test
Wall 4	Kaunos	All classes (Ashlar-dominant)	70 m ²	Cross-site generalization

Table 1: Properties of our test walls.

248 The wall facades of the test set are segmented using a sliding window approach with
249 overlapping patches (25% overlap, 960-pixel stride), unlike the pseudo-random Sobol sequence
250 used during training. This regular grid pattern ensures complete, systematic coverage of the test
251 walls.

252

253 To systematically evaluate the contribution of appearance and geometric information to
254 fortification masonry segmentation, we trained three variants of the model, each processing
255 different input channels while otherwise maintaining identical network architecture and hyper-
256 parameters:

257

258 1. **Appearance-only Model (4 channels):** Exclusively processing the RGB and alpha
259 channels from the orthomosaics, this baseline configuration relies solely on texture, color
260 variations, and shadow patterns to distinguish between blocks and masonry types.

261

262 2. **Geometry-only Model (3 channels):** This model uses only the normal maps derived from
263 heightmaps, focusing entirely on surface shape and orientation, while ignoring all visual
264 appearance. With this model, we test if surface orientation alone can differentiate between
265 single blocks and also different masonry types.

266

267 3. **Full Model (7 channels):** Our full approach concatenates both RGBA from orthomosaics
268 and XYZ from normal maps, hypothesizing that this fusion of visual and geometric features
269 would enhance classification performance.

270

271 This allows us to quantify both the individual and combined value of appearance and geometry
272 data. The geometry-only model tests whether surface orientation alone reveals core differences
273 between single blocks but also masonry types. Those differences are for instance the tight joints
274 of ashlar or polygonal masonry compared to quarry stones or the more uneven faces of polygonal
275 masonry and quarry stones compared to ashlar blocks. These features can still be visible in the
276 normal maps even when the faces are weathered or documented in different lighting conditions.
277 Meanwhile, the appearance-only model represents the current standard approach in
278 archaeological non-LiDAR image segmentation (Bellat et al. 2025: 10, 12, 18), providing a
279 benchmark against existing methodologies.

280

281 All three models were trained using identical hyper-parameters, loss functions, and the same
282 training/validation splits to ensure fair comparison.

283

284 We employed two complementary metrics that capture different aspects of segmentation
285 quality:

286

287 Intersection over Union (IoU) (Everingham et al. 2010; Jaccard 1901) measures the overlap
288 between predicted and ground truth segmentations for each class. Calculated as the area of
289 intersection divided by the area of union, IoU provides a strict evaluation where scores range from
290 0 (no overlap) to 1 (perfect overlap). This metric is particularly sensitive to both false positives and
291 false negatives, making it ideal for evaluating multiple archaeological stone classes with a demand
292 for high spatial accuracy. We calculated both per-class IoU and the mean IoU (mIoU).

293

294 The F1-Score (Rijsbergen 1979) balances precision and recall through their harmonic mean,
295 providing insight into the model's ability to correctly identify stones (precision) while not missing
296 any (recall). While IoU penalizes any spatial mismatch, F1-Score is more forgiving of minor
297 boundary errors, making it useful for understanding whether stones are being detected even if their
298 exact boundaries are imperfect. This distinction is important in archaeological contexts where
299 stone identification may be more critical than pixel-perfect boundary alignment for certain analytical
300 tasks.

294 Both metrics were calculated per wall and then averaged across the test set. For each wall, we
 295 computed metrics for all four classes (background, ashlar, polygonal, quarry stone) but focused
 296 our analysis on the three masonry classes, as background segmentation is trivial compared to
 297 distinguishing between different construction techniques.

298 **Results**

Model		Appearance only		Geometry only		Full Model	
		IoU	F1	IoU	F1	IoU	F1
Wall 1	Ashlar	.68	.81	.76	.86	.78	.88
	Polygonal	.37	.54	.44	.61	.65	.79
	Quarry	.16	.27	.32	.48	.37	.54
	All Classes	.40	.54	.51	.65	.60	.74
Wall 2	Ashlar	.81	.89	.81	.90	.85	.92
	Polygonal	–	–	–	–	–	–
	Quarry	.04	.08	.00	.00	.04	.07
	All Classes	.43	.49	.41	.45	.45	.50
Wall 3	Ashlar	–	–	–	–	–	–
	Polygonal	.78	.88	.81	.90	.78	.88
	Quarry	.21	.35	.29	.44	.31	.47
	All Classes	.50	.62	.37	.57	.55	.68
Wall 4	Ashlar	.83	.91	.71	.83	.82	.90
	Polygonal	.09	.16	.01	.02	.06	.12
	Quarry	.00	.00	.03	.05	.07	.14
	All Classes	.31	.36	.25	.30	.32	.39
All Walls	Ashlar	.77	.87	.76	.86	.82	.90
	Polygonal	.41	.53	.42	.51	.50	.60
	Quarry	.10	.18	.16	.24	.20	.31
	All Classes	.41	.50	.43	.52	.48	.58

Table 2: Quantitative results across models, test walls, and stone classes. Higher values indicate better performance. Bold numbers mark the best-performing model, while dashes denote classes absent from the test wall. The full model, which incorporates both appearance and geometry, generally achieves the best performance.

299 **Appearance-only Model** : The RGBA model, representing current standard practice in
 300 archaeological image segmentation, achieved a mean IoU of .41 across the test set. While
 301 demonstrating specific strengths, particularly in ashlar detection on Wall 4 with achieving the
 302 highest single-class IoU of .83, manual inspection reveals that the model failed to segment several
 303 stone's boundaries properly. This is particularly visible on Wall 1, where almost all vertical
 304 boundaries have not been detected (Fig. 7). The model struggled most significantly with quarry
 305 stone detection, achieving near-zero performance on Wall 4 and poor results elsewhere. F1-scores
 306 revealed high recall but low precision for several classes, indicating the model's tendency to over-
 307 segment, detecting stones beyond the annotated facade boundaries.

308
 309 **Geometry-only Model:** The normal map-based model achieved a mean IoU of .43 across all
 310 test walls, with notable variation between sites. Performance peaked on Wall 1, where the diverse
 311 masonry types provided sufficient geometric variation for differentiation. The model demonstrated
 312 particular strength in detecting ashlar blocks and polygonal masonry when present in substantial
 313 quantities. However, quarry stone detection remained problematic across all test cases. Wall 4
 314 proved especially challenging, suggesting that ashlar blocks with rather simple faces do not deliver
 315 sufficient geometry information for clear class division.

316

317 **Full Model:** Our proposed approach, concatenating appearance and geometry channels,
318 achieved the highest overall performance with mean IoU of .48 and mean F1-score of .58. The
319 model showed particular advantage on the complex Wall 1 with a 18% improvement over
320 geometry-only and 50% over appearance-only models. Ashlar detection remained consistently
321 strong, while polygonal and quarry stone classes showed improved but still variable performance.
322 Notably, the model achieved the best quarry stone detection on three of four test walls, with IoU
323 reaching .37 on Wall 1, though this class remained challenging overall.

324
325 When comparing the results, the evaluation reveals a clear performance hierarchy among the
326 three model configurations. The 7-channel combined model achieved the highest average
327 performance, demonstrating a 12% improvement over the geometry-only model and 17% over the
328 appearance-only model .

329 The most revealing test case is Wall 1, which contains all three masonry classes in meaningful
330 proportions. Here, the 7-channel model achieved a mean IoU of .60, significantly outperforming
331 both the geometry-only and appearance-only variants. This wall represents the ideal scenario
332 where the complementary nature of visual and geometric features can be fully leveraged.

333 The evaluation statistics reveal complex performance patterns that reflect both model
334 capabilities and dataset characteristics:

335 Ashlar blocks demonstrate the most consistent detection across all models, benefiting from
336 their regular geometric properties and substantial representation in the training data.

337 Polygonal blocks show a bimodal performance pattern directly tied to their presence in the test
338 walls. When polygonal masonry comprises a significant portion of the wall, all models perform well
339 (Fig. 8). However, the performance drop on Wall 4 reflects the statistical impact of minimal
340 polygonal presence (Fig. 9).

341 Quarry stones reveal a critical training artifact: the models have learned to associate quarry
342 stones with polygonal blocks, as these classes frequently co-occur in the training data. This
343 learned correlation explains why quarry stone detection improves in walls with substantial
344 polygonal masonry (Fig. 6) but fails almost entirely when polygonal blocks are absent (Fig. 9). The
345 consistently low IoU scores also reflect severe pixel-level class imbalance.

346
347 While IoU and F1-scores provide standardized performance measures, they fail to capture
348 several aspects critical for archaeological analysis:

349 Boundary precision between individual stones is essential for archaeological documentation
350 and affects only a small percentage of total pixels and thus barely impacts the metrics. Visual
351 inspection reveals that the 7-channel model produces significantly cleaner stone boundaries than
352 the appearance-only model, with the geometry-only model falling between them (Fig. 7).

353
354 Out-of-masonry-bond detections present another metric limitation. All models detect stones
355 visible in the image but not part of the annotated target facade – collapsed blocks, background
356 walls, or adjacent structures (Fig. 10). While these technically count as false positives and reduce
357 the metrics, they represent correct stone identifications. These identifications can be easily filtered
358 in post-processing if needed and do not indicate model failures.

Figure 6: Qualitative results for our test walls, showing inputs (left), semantic segmentation from our full model, and manual annotations (right). Color coding of block types follows the scheme in Fig. 1; black denotes background. Best viewed digitally and at high magnification. Another example of subsection (text in PCJ Subsection style)

Figure 7: Boundary precision between individual stones on Wall 1.

Figure 8: Polygonal-dominant Wall 2.

Figure 9: Small-sample effects on Wall 4.

Figure 10: Out-of-masonry-bond detections on Wall 1.

361 Small-sample effects dramatically impact the metrics for minority classes. When polygonal
362 blocks or quarry stones are sparse, even a few incorrectly classified blocks severely impact IoU
363 scores, making the metrics overly sensitive to individual errors rather than reflecting overall model
364 capability.

365
366 Wall 4 provides insights into model robustness across regional variations. The overall
367 performance decrease initially suggests poor generalization. However, this largely reflects the
368 extreme class imbalance in the Wall 4 facade rather than fundamental model failure. The wall
369 facade consists of almost only ashlar blocks, which are mostly segmented correctly (IoU: .82, F1:
370 .90) . The low scores derive mainly from out-of-masonry-bond detections and small-sample effects
371 visible on top of the wall facade (Fig. 9).

372
373 These preliminary results, achieved without class balancing or loss function optimization,
374 already demonstrate the viability of our dual-layer approach for archaeological documentation. The
375 consistent performance advantage over single-layer alternatives confirms that our methodology
376 captures complementary information essential for masonry analysis.

377 The identified issues, class imbalance effects, correlations between quarry stones and
378 polygonal blocks, and sensitivity to minority classes are well-understood problems with established
379 solutions. Implementing class balancing strategies and optimizing the entropy/dice loss ratio
380 should address these limitations. Additionally, expanding the training dataset, particularly for
381 underrepresented classes, will further improve model robustness.

382 Despite current limitations, the models already show practical utility. The ability to achieve .60
383 IoU on complex walls like Wall 1 without optimization suggests that, once refined, these tools will
384 significantly accelerate archaeological documentation workflows. The systematic nature of current
385 errors makes them predictable and manageable through post-processing, while continued training
386 will reduce their frequency.

387 **Future Directions**

388
389 The identified class imbalance and correlation issues will be addressed through class balancing
390 strategies and cross-entropy/dice loss ratio optimization. Expanding the training dataset will help
391 with underrepresented masonry types in certain wall sections.

392 We will develop specialized metrics for archaeologically relevant features. For gap detection
393 accuracy, morphological closing operations (Serra 1982) on ground-truth background masks to
394 isolate joints between stones. Calculating gap-specific IoU will provide meaningful evaluation of
395 joint detection.

396
397 The segmentation model represents the first component of a comprehensive analytical
398 framework. The second part of the pipeline will transform pixel-level outputs into block-level
399 geometric descriptions, extracting shape descriptors (aspect ratios, surface areas, corner angles)
400 and analyzing facade-level patterns including block type distributions, stretcher-binder patterns,
401 and construction clusters. Recent studies (Fontana and Bernard 2023) validated such quantitative
402 approaches but were limited to small samples due to manual documentation. Our automated
403 pipeline enables similar analyses at vastly larger scales, processing kilometer-long fortifications in
404 minutes rather than days. This enables analysis of construction sequences, regional typologies,
405 and structural stability assessments, helping understand construction practices, potentially
406 identifying building units, and revealing temporal phases within fortification systems.

407
408 Upon publication, the complete framework will be released as open-source software with a
409 graphical user interface, ensuring accessibility to archaeologists regardless of technical expertise.
410 This democratization of advanced analytical capabilities aligns with broader movements toward

411 open science in archaeology, ensuring that the benefits of machine-learning applications extend
412 beyond individual research projects.

413 **Conclusion**

414 This paper addressed a fundamental challenge in modern archaeological practice: the
415 increasing gap between growing 3D documentation capabilities and our capacity for systematic
416 analysis. While photogrammetric surveys of ancient fortifications routinely generate terabytes of
417 data, manual interpretation methods remain time-consuming and subjective. Our dual-layer
418 pipeline transforms this passive visual record into an active analytical tool by leveraging both
419 appearance and geometric information from 3D documentation.

420 The methodological innovation lies in combining high-resolution orthomosaics with geometry-
421 based normal maps derived from photogrammetric models. This approach preserves both visual
422 texture and critical surface orientation information in a format suitable for standard CNN
423 architectures. Unlike previous approaches that rely solely on appearance data or broad
424 topographic features, our method captures fine-scale surface geometry essential for distinguishing
425 between masonry types even under changing lighting conditions or varying states of preservation.

426 Our evaluation demonstrates clear performance advantages: the combined 7-channel model
427 achieved a mean IoU of .48, representing a 17% improvement over appearance-only models and
428 12% over geometry-only approaches. On walls containing all three masonry classes, the combined
429 model reached .60 mIoU – 50% better than appearance-only segmentation. These results confirm
430 that visual and geometric features provide complementary information essential for robust
431 masonry analysis.

432 Despite current limitations – primarily class imbalance effects and learned correlations between
433 co-occurring masonry types – the models demonstrate practical utility for archaeological
434 documentation. The systematic nature of errors makes them manageable through post-
435 processing, while planned improvements will enhance performance. The ability to process
436 kilometer-long fortifications in minutes rather than weeks transforms fortification studies from
437 selective sampling to comprehensive analysis of entire defensive systems.

438 This work represents a concrete step in archaeology's digital transformation, addressing the
439 critical gap identified by Magnani et al. (Magnani et al. 2020: 737) regarding photogrammetry's
440 underutilized analytical potential. Moving beyond documentation toward automated analysis
441 enables systematic comparative studies across sites and periods at unprecedented scales. As the
442 framework matures and training datasets expand, automated analysis promises to reveal new
443 insights about ancient construction practices, regional building traditions, and temporal
444 developments in defensive architecture.

445 **Conflict of interest disclosure**

446 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest
447 in relation to the content of the article.

448 **Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability**

449 All code needed to implement the method presented in this study is available at
450 <https://github.com/NilsSchnorr/AppearanceMeetsGeometry>.

451 All data is available under DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17011862.

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